

Multi-year yield map generator – An open source software tool for modeling multi-year yield maps

Marco Donat^{1,2}, Jonas Geistert¹, Kathrin Grahmann¹
and Sonoko D. Bellingrath-Kimura^{1,2}

¹Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Eberswalder Str. 84, 15374 Müncheberg, Germany; ²Institute of Agriculture and Horticulture, Faculty of Life Science, Humboldt University of Berlin, Albrecht-Thaer-Weg 5, 14195 Berlin, Germany. E-Mail: Marco.Donat@zalf.de

Introduction

Yield maps have become an essential element in precision agriculture to optimize cropping systems and provide information to quantify yield variability. Methods have already been established for filtering and cleaning yield maps generated from combine harvester and identifying management zones. However, these methods have very often been validated with multiannual yield maps that are not publicly available, making comparison between individual methods difficult.

The aim of this study was to develop an open source software tool that realistically models plant yields. Generated yield values correlate spatially and temporally and can be adapted to different use cases by several parameters. Own field geometries can be used. The tool was developed as a module and can be installed using standardized package managers for Python (e.g. *pip*). Generated multi-year yield maps can be used to create data set for new methods to identify management zones.

Material and Methods

The open source software tool was developed in the *Python* programming language. To create multi-year yield maps, a yield value $yield(x,y,t)$ is calculated for each spatial point within a three-dimensional matrix using the following formula:

$$yield(x, y, t) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^c v_i * e^{-d_i(x,y,t)}}{\sum_{i=0}^c e^{-d_i(x,y,t)}} \quad [\text{Equation 1}]$$

with v_i being the kernel coefficient of the i -th kernel and e the exponential function from the negative distance to the i -th kernel d_i , which is calculated as followed:

$$d_i(x, y, t) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{(x - x_i)}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{(y - y_i)}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{(t - t_i)}{b_t}\right)^2} \quad [\text{Equation 2}]$$

where x,y are the spatial and t the temporal position of the respective point, and x_i,y_i are the spatial and t_i the temporal position of the i -th kernel, b is the scaling factor for the spatial dimension and b_t is the scaling factor for the temporal dimension. The generated yields are subsequently standardized to relative yield values. The yield correlates spatially as well as temporally and can be regulated in its variability via parameters b and b_t . To validate the tool, generated data sets (rand) were compared with real multi-year yield maps from one field (real) for 5 growing seasons each. The cleaning from erroneous data points of raw yield maps was done according to Donat et al. (2022). To test the autocorrelation of the data sets, spatial autocorrelation Moran's I statistic with a distance weights matrix (radius of 40 m) was used. To test for small-scale variation, experimental and fitted variograms were compared. To test

the temporal-spatial stability of normalized yield data, statistical grid pointwise analysis using σ over time was applied (Donat et al. 2022).

Results and discussion

The tool is available as download in an open source repository (Multi-year yield map generator, 2023). Validation with real yield maps showed minor deviations from modeled yields in terms of spatial and temporal variability. Temporal stability analysis showed that the field (real) contained 246 data points with $\sigma > 30$, whereas field (rand) contained 221 data points with $\sigma > 30$ and thus classified as unstable (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Temporal stability map of all 5 growing seasons with standard deviation of all data points. A) Field (real) and B) Field (rand).

Overall, 54.0% of all grid points of the field (real) showed high and stable yields, 38.5% low and stable yields and 7.5% unstable yields. For the field (rand), 46.0% of all grid points showed high and stable yields, 47.0% low and stable yields and 7.0% unstable yields. The annual yields of the field (real) showed significant global Moran values of 0.73, 0.66, 0.72, 0.72, and 0.66. Similar global autocorrelation was found for the field (rand) with values of 0.83, 0.77, 0.78, 0.79 und 0.75 for each year, respectively.

Table 1. Parameters of best fitted variogram models of multi-year yield maps of field (real) and field (rand)

	Year1	Year2	Year3	Year4	Year5
Field (real)					
Fitted Model	Stable	Stable	Matern	Matern	Matern
Range [m]	138	115	197	168	115
Sill	453	1349	660	508	367
RMSE	9.92	48.2	11.9	11.4	8.1
Field (rand)					
Fitted Model	Matern	Gaussian	Matern	Stable	Gaussian
Range [m]	150	122	133	108	115
Sill	621	523	672	426	482
RMSE	14.3	16.9	18.0	11.2	24.4

Variogram analyses of relative yield values showed strong spatial correlation of yield data for both data sets (Table 1). For both fields, similar ranges of spatial dependency between 108 m and a maximum of 197m were found.

This tool can be used to validate and compare methods of yield map cleaning, spatial

interpolation, and management zone creation.

Acknowledgements

This work was realized through funding from the Digital Agriculture Knowledge and Information System (DAKIS) Project (031B0729A), financed by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF).

References

- Multi-year yield map generator (2023). (<https://github.com/mardonat/Multi-year-yield-map-generator>)
 Donat, M., et al. (2022). "Patch cropping-a new methodological approach to determine new field arrangements that increase the multifunctionality of agricultural landscapes." *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 197: 106894